

Mental Security and Health in the Lean Sustainable Enterprise: the corporate psychological responsibility

Sécurité mentale et santé dans l'entreprise Lean Sustainable: la responsabilité psychologique de l'entreprise

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Abstract

One of the most complex CSR components is the employees 'psychological and mental health'. Indeed, CSR principles and practices cover key elements related to employees' motivation and satisfaction that are relevant efficiency and performance drivers. Moreover, in a Lean performance system employees are considered to be the key success element. However, this management model has fallen under multiple constraints in many firms. In this article, we aim to highlight the importance of positive work climate, ethics and values to increase employee's productivity and satisfaction especially in rigid and strict work environments. This article is based on the experience of Lean sustainable management considered to be a philosophy of respecting employees' capacities at driving strategic change in the firms. What is especially covered in this article is the compulsory need for managers to give more importance to employees' mental wellbeing as a profound CSR approach rather than responding only to social and environmental needs. We are addressing by this issue the impact of psychological management as a strategic management in building a sustainable approach to human resources development.

Key words: CSR, Lean management, Sustainable Lean Management, Corporate mental health; Psychological management, Strategic management.

Résumé

Une des composantes les plus complexes à appréhender dans la Responsabilité sociale des entreprises est la sécurité morale et mentale des employés. En effet, les éléments et les pratiques de la RSE couvrent les éléments liés à la motivation et à la satisfaction des employés qui sont l'efficacité et la performance. En plus, dans un système Lean, ces employés sont considérés comme les éléments de réussite, bien que ce modèle tant réussi ait connu des échecs considérables en termes de management des employés. Dans cet article, nous nous attachons à mettre en lumière l'importance du climat de travail positif, les valeurs et l'éthique afin d'améliorer la productivité et la satisfaction des employés notamment dans les espaces de travail rigides. Nous avons choisi le modèle du Lean management durable qui constitue une alliance exemplaire entre travail stricte et respect des Hommes. A travers la problématique traitée dans cet article, nous adressons une nouvelle approche de la RSE qui est la prise en charge de l'élément psychologique longtemps négligée par les managers et faiblement étudié par les travaux de recherche abordant la RSE tandis qu'elle est uniquement abordée par les recherches axées sur la psychologie du travail.

Mots clés : RSE, Lean management, Lean Management Durable, Santé mental des entreprises; Management psychologique, Management stratégique.

Introduction

In 1970, Adam Smith wrote a book about Firm's Empathy as a value creation driver. It was the result of multiple philosophical questions and research above the way firms can be assertive in their societies. Five years after, Adam Smith emphasized the need for firms to be competitive and make economic efficiencies. Today, we observe a world driven by human interests and powerful groups that decide what value is and what is not. In 1984, Edward Freeman invented "the stakeholder approach" when he published his worthy book entitled: Strategic Management: the stakeholder approach (Freeman, 2010). He insisted in the presence of different groups of interest rather than the existence of shareholders as parts directly involved in value creation and profit. Indeed, many parts and groups contribute to the definition of the value in the firms process and influence the conception of products and services, furthermore they influence the value chain permanently each one in its interest area. But there is one part or group of interest that has its hands on the value chain constantly and participates in the definition, the conception and the delivery of this value; it's the employees. This group of stakeholders can be hard to manage since it is directly in confrontation with the whole value chain and can be a factor of success or failure. Even when the firm has defined its stakeholders, their needs, their level of power and interest, and has elaborated and well refined its business model and action plans, the employees component can be devastating if they don't fit firm's ethics and values, are not recruited according to an integrative recruitment plan that joins skills to ethics, wages policy is not motivating, social climate is hard, internal communication methods are weak. We can refer all these elements to psychological factors that are major keys in choosing and keeping the best team for the value creation especially in hard environments such as the Lean environment that demands great respect of operational excellence principles, great respect to achieving goals and employee's expertise and 0 errors. Employee's morale can be the solution to decrease the impacts of such rigid work, even with well implemented social practices to make employees psychologically satisfied, outputs such as stress, conflicts and health problems arise sooner or later to put emphasis on the limit between social practices and psychological factors that can devastate motivation and morale.

Problem formulation:

Lean Sustainable Management is the perfect management model in today's firms seeking global performance and global stakeholder's satisfaction. Is this perfect combination enough to sustain employees' motivation and mental well-being especially in a rigid work

environment such as the Lean one? Are CSR practices considered to be solutions for such environment?

The goal of this article is to determine the gap or the link between CSR, Lean Management and positive psychology, supposing the following hypothesis: Lean management combined to CSR practices leads to Psychological Health & Security.

To explore this problematic issue, this article will put light on the definition of Lean Management, and whether it is a source of motivation or stress in the work environment, then we will present the core theories and approaches that treat employees' motivation. We intend also to define the sustainable Lean approach based on taking into account employees psychological and physical health and security by exploring the Lean framework advantages and constraints through a survey among a sample of 109 Moroccan industrial firms with different sizes.

Questions:

- What is the exact difference between social impact and psychological impact in CSR strategies?
- What is the definition of a Corporate Psychological Responsibility? Why psychology management is needed in firms?
- Are CSR practices enough to increase employee's satisfaction?
- Is Lean sustainable management a driver for employee's satisfaction?
- What are psychological drivers for employee's motivation?

1. Lean Management

1.1 Is Lean Management a source of motivation or stress?

The whole Lean Management philosophy is about chasing waste in all forms and seeking perfection constantly: 0 inventory, 0 waste, 0 defects, 0 waiting time. These Zeros or rather perfection goals are considered to be the most reasons of stress and mental health problems since they are challenging employees in daily manner. In cultures different than the Japanese one, this research of perfection can be the cause of high turnovers, absenteeism, sickness, employees' conflicts and sabotage; they are even becoming arguments for licensing employees who didn't achieve firm's objectives. While the paradox that relies under the Lean cap is that the philosophy itself as created in Japan makes human resources as top of firm's consideration. The table 1 below shows the Lean's principles role in maintaining motivation and good morale:

Table 1: Lean principles consistency

Principles	Lean consistency
Leadership	The Lean leader plays the role of a martial arts sensei or master, he doesn't only make strategies and decisions but teaches employees how to be loyal and gain trust on the firm's values and goals.
Coaching	Managers are teachers, not only they monitor teams on how to master tools and principles but teach them how to challenge themselves morally and operationally. Perfection is achievable as long as the system is provided with skilled employees.
Gensu Gembutsu	Managers and CEOs have horizontal communication with teams; they visit the plants and speak directly to employees. Multiple communication levels are source of bias to the original information. Operational employees are Solutions providers since they know the process or the machine more than managers themselves.
Training	Training is a vital need and not an advantage or a reward. In the Lean philosophy, training employees is not only for the firm but also for self-esteem and the return on investment is greater than the investment itself.
Expertise	Continuous learning is one of the powerful principles of the Lean enterprise since it encourages employees to seek and use data and technologies to optimize process.
Kanban or design thinking	During Kanban sessions operational teams are very important to suggest solutions and generate progress.
VM	This principle highlights the constant information of employees about goals and achievements. Principle information and data is shared visually for employees to prevail the rise of informal communication that is a source of misunderstandings among the employees.
POKE YOKE	This principle highlights the measures taken by the firm to lock the errors provenance or likelihood and insists on the fact that rather than wasting time in problems resolution it is better to exploit that time on process optimization and innovation.

Source: (Toyota Production System Handbook, 2008)

Some research papers (Kihel & Harbal, 2020) highlighted the psychological effect of Lean Management in the work environment considered to be the opposite of the "employee's motivation principle":

Table 2: Lean tools and their impact on motivation

Lean tools	Impact on motivation
MUDA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 0 inventory: urgent commands or specific commands with no security inventory can cause employees' stress who is located in the intersection with many parts such as the client, the managers the suppliers and the freight transporters. - 0 defects: to conceive products with no defects the employees must master each point of the process and anticipate any machine malfunctioning, incompetency, defects mean that the process lacks quality which generates additional costs and time wasting. - 0 unnecessary moves: are considered to be source of communication problems, and health problems due to maintaining same body moves on a daily manner.
JAT (INRS , 2015)	The JAT principle is the basic principle among the Lean invention. This principle is the most difficult to handle since it reconfigures the whole value chain of the firm and can demand years of process reshaping and reviewing. In this many years' employees can see themselves working for a goal that is not seen yet and experience multiple criticism and revisiting the process. Managers can be perceived as supervisors and not as solution providers.
SMED	With many series change, employees see themselves changing products and raw material each time, as the name shows it, it is about 1 minute or more of serial change time where employees must play in a course against time repeatedly; this generates what we call the SMED anxiety and stress.

CELLULE U	In these work units, employees and machines operating in the same operational systems, process or products are located in the same area or location to prevent the unnecessary employee's placements and moves. But this situation creation monotony, communication loss with teams located in the other units, isolation and team's competitiveness in a negative way. In addition to that, machines can be source of auditive problems and migraine.
Polyvalence	Many tasks and roles for employees (Hasle & Bojesen (2012))
Perfection	Many tests (Hasle & Bojesen, 2012))
Team Work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task change, team frequent organization (Conti & al. (2006)) • Doing absent employee's tasks (Hasle & Bojesen (2012)) • Competitive work climate (INRS (2015))

Source: Compilation from (INRES, 2015); (Hasle & Bojesen, 2012);(Conti & al. 2006)

If Lean is implemented without pre-steps or change management, this can create a negative work climate (Table 2). But first, let's underline elements of a negative work environment. Table 3 links elements of negative work environment to each strategic level of the firm.

Table 3: Consistency of strategic levels

Strategic Level	Lean negative impacts by strategic levels
Business	Absence of leadership, values, ethics has a relationship with founders of the company who don't give much importance or neglect psychological impact of their firm's decisions, actions and plans on employees.
Operations	Tools methods are the origin of stress such in lean management, objectives are defined without considering their effect on employees in terms of time of execution, how to execute them, final results are the only results to be recognized, small realizations are not seen or considered.
Functions	Management is not trained to manage conflicts, communication problems, the existence of vertical communication rather than horizontal communication, information is purposely not shared.

Source: Authors

While these gaps exist in firm's strategy, social practices are not enough to fill in these gaps especially with highly sensitive employees. While these emotional employees can be solution precursors for multiple problems facing the business, the firm can experience losing them to integrate other work environments that offer them less wages, trainings, positions but better mental health and positive psychological impact.

2. Psychological is beyond social

While Lean Management is not the best business model for employee's motivation endorsement, firms tend to overcome its psychological effects such as stress and anxiety by linking it to CSR practices. Actually, social practices are drivers for employees' motivation, but are they psychological drivers for mental health and security? What is mental health & security anyway?

2.1 Psychological H&S in the work environment:

One of the first questions that employees ask before reaching their office desk or station in a workplace is: How is social climate in this firm? A question that is related to employee's state of relationships and managers behavior and ethics. In a workplace known by conflictual disturbance and the absence of human resources management in terms of behaviors and values, and even with the presence of social advantages, employees are more likely to abandon even great job opportunities once they struggle with negative social climate impacts. That leads us to identify negative psychological elements and their impact on employee's satisfaction and motivation even in a firm that embraces an effective Lean CSR strategy.

Table 4: Consistency of theories of motivation

Theories	Consistency
Theory of needs (Maslow 1940)	Maslow has stated a hierarchy of needs to be fulfilled from the bottom of a pyramid until the top with these needs: physiological needs, safety, membership and security, esteem and finally self-accomplishment (Fyans, 2004)
Vroom expectancy motivation theory (1964)	Vroom's expectancy theory assumes that behavior results from conscious choices among alternatives whose purpose is to maximize pleasure and to minimize pain. Vroom realized that an employee's performance is based on individual factors such as personality, skills, knowledge, experience and abilities. He stated that effort, performance and motivation are linked in a person's motivation. He uses the variables Expectancy, Instrumentality and Valence to account for this.
Hertzberg's two factor theory (1959)	The two factors identified by Herzberg are motivators and hygiene factors. 1. Motivating Factors: The presence of motivators causes employees to work harder. They are found within the actual job itself 2. Hygiene Factors: The absence of hygiene factors will cause employees to work less hard. Hygiene factors are not present in the actual job itself but surround the job.
McClelland's theory of needs (1987)	It is s one such theory that explains this process of motivation by breaking down what and how needs are and how they have to be approached. David McClelland was an American Psychologist who developed his theory of needs or Achievement Theory of Motivation which revolves around three important aspects, namely, Achievement, Power and Affiliation.
McGregor's theory X and theory Y (1960)	Douglas McGregor formulated Theory X and Theory Y suggesting two aspects of human behavior at work, or in other words, two different views of individuals (employees): one of which is negative, called as Theory X and the other is positive, so called as Theory Y. According to McGregor, the perception of managers on the nature of individuals is based on various assumptions.

Source: Compilation from (Vroom, 1964); (Hertzber, 1959); (McClelland, 1987) ; (Mc Cregor, 1960).

Motivation theories shown in table 4 are vital for economic development and process performance in every organization. While classic management approaches emphasis on operational management and scientific work organization, contemporary school management is aware that work instructions are easily handled by happy employees. The Hawthorne experiment (Elton Mayo, 1935-1937) is the best example, even if criticized

among academics, that show how paying attention to employees can change their behavior.

2.2 Sustainable Lean:

The best definition of the sustainable lean enterprise is the enterprise that implemented social practices in order to retain employees especially those whom the enterprise has already trained and conceived as process or product experts, to decrease absenteeism, and turnover, and to attract potential skilled employees especially those with rare skills in the super market. Managers and CEOs recognize today that value creation begins with recruiting the best team after product definition in the business model. To create value for clients, enterprises must create values first for employees. We add to the social practices, environmental management system that adjusts the way firm shapes process environmentally in order to deliver an eco-friendly product. A sustainable Lean is then conceived as the integration of social practices sufficient enough to create a positive impact in employee's mindset and overcome stress and anxiety. A survey conducted in a sample of 109 Moroccan industrial firms shows that specific tools are related to specific social practices. Indeed, the study of linkage between Lean and social practices, and the generation of stress and conflicts showed as some facts.

3. Survey scope:

A sample of 109 Moroccan industrial firms with different sizes was asked about:

- *What lean tools are used in different process?*
- *What social practices are implemented in order to increase employees' performance?*
- *What are the economic reasons that guided toward implementing Lean tools?*
- *What are the social reasons that guided toward implementing Lean tools?*
- *What Social constraints are generated after implementing Lean Tools?*

Characteristics of the sample:

The sample is composed of 68% of SMEs and 32, 2% of Groups as shown in table 5.

Table 5: Sample composition

		Percent
Valid	<=200	68,8
	>200	31,2
	Total	100,0

Source: Authors

It includes the following industrial sectors:

Table 6: Industrial sectors composition in the sample

Industrial sectors	Percent
AERONAUTIC	10,1%
TRANSPORT	4,6%
TEXTILE	10,1%
METALLURGY	15,6%
PLASTIC and SCRAB	27,5%
AGROFEED	12,8%
CHEMICALS	10,1%
ELECTRICIC & ELECTRONIC	9,2%
TOTAL	100,0%

Source: Authors

Question n°1: What are Lean Management tools used in process:

Only 57 firms apply lean management which represents 51 of the firms in the sample. The distribution of tools application between the firms implementing Lean Management is:

Table 7: Tools use in sample firms process

Tools	% application
JAT	40%
Time Cycle Reduction	44%
POKE YOKE	37%
KAIZEN	42%
KANBAN	34%
SMED	37%
JIDOKA	63%
TPM	84%
STANDARADISATION	71%
VSM	61%
Management visuel	56%
TAKT TIME	32%
Unités autonomes de production	40%
HEIJ UNKA	21%
GEMBA	25%

Source: Authors

From Table 7 we observe that tools such as: JIDOKA, TPM, STANDARDIZATION, VSM and VISUAL MANAGEMENT are mostly used among the other tools. This can be explained by the easiness of their implementation in comparison to tools such as: JAT, POKE YOKE, KAIZEN...etc.

Question n° 2: What social practices are associated with Lean Management tools:

Using SPSS tools and Principal Component Analysis, we extract the following social practices and lean tools combinations in table 8:

Table 8: Lean Tools and their association with social practices and psychological impact

Tools	Social practices associated
STANDARDISATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Job and skills Planning - Annual training planning - Work accidents planning - Disabledworkersrecruitment - Complaints management
VISUAL MANAGEMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Annual training planning - Work accidents planning - Disabledworkersrecruitment
JIDOKA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work accidents planning - Complaints management - After sales management - Health and security management
CYCLE TIME REDUCTION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Job and Competency Planning - Annual training planning - Work accidents planning - DisabledWorks recruitment - Complaints management
VSM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - After sales management - Complaints management - Work accidents planning
POKE YOKE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Job and skills Planning - Annual training planning - Work accidents planning - Disabled workers recruitment - Complaints management
JUST IN TIME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Job and skills Planning - Annual training planning - Work accidents planning - Disabled workers recruitment - Complaints management - Health
HEIJUNKA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - After sales management - Health management - Job and skills Planning - Work accidents planning - Complaints management

Source: Authors

Combinations shown in table 8 might change if the sample characteristics (firm's size, industrial sectors) change. We observe that some social practices are vital to some tools. If we analyze how tools impact the implementation of social practices, we create the following combination: Firms see themselves engaged with these social practices in order to help them manage tools, not having these tools can be a source of multiple risks in terms of skills weakness, health problems, accidents and absenteeism...etc.

Question n°2: What are economic and social motivators that guided you toward Lean Management?

By asking this question our aim is to detect the importance degree given to economic motives and social motives prior to implementing the Lean tools and depict if social motives have the same importance as economic motives.

Table 9: Economic motives for Lean implementation and their impact on employees

Economic motivators	Very important	Important	Less important
Continuous improvement	96%	0%	4%
Cost reduction	95%	5%	0%
Incomes increasing	88%	12%	0%
Time reduction	93%	7%	0%
Inventory reduction	82%	4%	14%
Quality improvement	100%	0%	0%
Defects reduction	93%	5%	2%
Machines breakdowns reduction	96%	4%	0%
Satisfaction des clients	100%	0%	0%

Source: Authors

Economic motivators in table 9 are seen as major motivators that drive firms in implementing Lean Tools. This is the logical purpose by any waste reduction since firms are created generate financial profit, any type of optimization: time, cost or process can be considered as a financial gain. In the contrary, social motivators gain less importance as shown in the table 10 below:

Table10: Social motives importance in implementing Lean Management

Social motivators	Very important	Important	Less important
Employees' Motivation	14%	58%	28%
Skill empowerment	14%	46%	40%
Team work empowerment	19%	56%	42%

Source: Authors

We detected only 3 main social motives that don't exceed 19 of firms claiming the importance. Economic motives appear to be the priority of all firms. We consider that result as the normal goal firms seek by implementing Lean tools but we deduct that while sitting economic objectives firms tend not to consider the employees well-being by not integrating personal objectives inside economic objectives such as motivation, skills empowerment and work team settling. That is considered to be the common mistake why economic optimization methods and tools tend to fail when they are economically directed, while economic objectives are to be achieved by employees themselves, implementation must begin in employees' heads before the process.

Question n°3. What Social constraints are generated after implementing Lean Tools?

Employees being asked about direct outputs posterior to implementing Lean tools, named four direct outputs that are:

Table 11: Social constraints generated by implementing Lean Management

Réponse	Stress	Conflicts	Tasks multiplicity	Health problems
Yes	96%	46%	72%	7%
No	4%	54%	28%	93%

Source: Authors

We observe in table 11 that stress is the dominant output, followed by task multiplicity then conflicts. Health problems were less cited because most firms are aware of employees' health measures by engaging a medical service check out regularly. We insist in the health problems output that it doesn't include psychological impacts such as the lack of morale or indirect output of stress.

Question n°6: Did you receive any training prior to Lean implementation?

Employees were also asked about Lean trainings sessions taken in order to enable them to implement Lean principles:

Table 12: Lean training prevalence

Lean Training	
YES	NO
81%	19%

Source: Authors

Table 12 shows that 81% of the firms received a practical training about Lean principles and tools, while 19% engaged experts in charge of the Lean project. However, these trainings remain practical and don't instruct managers and employees about the Lean Management philosophy in terms of change conduct and employees' integration. As a result of strategies that don't put the employee in the heart of the change, problems related to motivation, stress, communication disturbance, conflicts are the obvious outcome, that leads to productivity decrease and quality problems that ruin not only internal process but also the firm's reputation.

4. Key measures for a better psychological work climate in Lean sustainable firm:

This section tends to present major elements to implement for a better psychological impact of firms process on employee's psychological wellbeing.

4.1 Psychological measures

To be able to characterize a firm as "psychologically responsible", we need to observe basic psychological measures that help enhance better work conditions such as:

4.1.1 Leadership:

Leadership is a word that defines management staff ability to conduct potential projects and goals of a firm with efficiency. But this concept goes beyond implying a great corporate performance and positive results; it is an idealistic word that is related to management actions and practices that enhance employee's self-confidence, unexpected achievements and self-esteem. A leader is a feeder with key elements to training, expertise and knowledge gain. He is conceived as a family father that teaches his children principles, hard work and respect until they become capable of transmitting it to others. Unfortunately, leadership courses and techniques haven't been able yet to spot the light on this "miner" element that can be a source of superior performance. Hence, leaders with lack of behavioral techniques for employees fail to create a better work experience and can be perceived as pragmatic managers

seeking tangible results without giving much importance to the psychological side of productivity. Employees then tend to perceive them as distant and non-communicating. In the Lean Manufacturing principles, leadership plays a great role in federating employees into goals. “Respect of the people”, “Coaching” and “building people then building work” are major principles that made the success of the lean philosophy in the TPS in Japan, otherwise, implementing rigid and rigorous tools such as lean tools would have been a defeat.

4.1.2 Recruitment mechanism:

A firm defines “job descriptions” for each task to be fulfilled, but recruitment policies must not only cover academic and trainings requirements that candidates must fulfill, they must also highlight corporate values. Recruitment staff must be prepared and trained to hire employees that will not affect their firm negatively as recruitment is the entry process of employees into the firm; these employees are the actors that create such a social climate. Not hired person are to be reached for better performance in the next

4.1.2 Categorized employees Potential and talent

Not using social and psychological techniques to recognize types of potentials: it is essential for employers to integrate coaches and psychologists to determine employees mind functioning. We refer here to type of employee’s abilities to handle tasks, for example in each task, team must be organized as: concept conceivers, practitioners and communicators. We can template this categorization to a classroom where the teacher defines types of potentials or intelligences among his students: cognitive intelligence, social intelligence, visual intelligence ... it is a necessary step to defining how to use each employee in the right point in the value chain. Employers with low Emotional Intelligence are less capable of making right decisions and are more likely to fire employees especially in a lean platform. That is why the lean sustainable platform is necessary in a workplace that uses lean principles and tools.

4.1.4 Identified corporate values and ethics:

Not identifying values is a great mistake. When a firm defines its major ideologies in terms of for example our vocation is not harming the environment, citizenship and participate in the society development, integrating this ideology into the employee’s mind is by organizing meetings that spread information related to this subjects, visual management, integrating it as a slogan incremented into employee’s minds in a daily basis.

4.1.5 Permanent integrity and unicity:

Vanishing isolated work even in isolated platforms such as artificial intelligence platforms or U cells or units is compulsory for employee's social climate.

5. A framework for firms' Psychological responsibility:

In order to enhance firm's capability of optimizing stress and vanishing psychological impacts on employees as a "potential waste", firms need to apply standards that assess their compliance with "psychological quality" of the overall firm behavior. Indeed, like environmental management system, or quality management, CSR, employee's psychology should be taken into consideration while defining products and process and should be assessed as a guarantee of "firm's image". In a world driven by multiple crisis such as the economic crisis of 2007, the COVID 19 pandemic impacts on social and economic international firms, employees seek today the most reliable firm to be in terms of respecting their social rights and the best treatment in difficult times: social coverage and work stability even during crisis. Firms can refer to psychological experts to identify types of psychological elements to take into consideration in managing and solving employees' issues for a better work climate and satisfaction. Table 13 is indeed a set of management guidelines to draw and implement by managers for a better work climate.

Table 13: Interaction between psychological elements and lean & social management

Person Centric philosophy	Consistency	Intersection with lean management and social management
Values recognition and establishment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Settling and formalizing values and ethics to be respected by employees (values can be structured on a document that can be signed by employees in recognition to their engagement toward the belief and the application of such moral values) 	Respecting people Product compliance Client satisfaction and employee satisfaction
Relational management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Planning inter-teams' tasks and switching employees into groups permanently and in respect to process - Managing - Vanishing bullying 	Gensu Gembutsu Conflicts management
Esteem management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rewarding achievements and encouraging employees into ...their capacities - Training employees on personality and specific development modules: oral communication, soft skills, hard skills, enhancing the 	Kanban Permanent Coaching and training
Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Salaries are offered in regard to the fulfillments after taking into consideration psychological drivers - Firm is capable of handling periods of financial and economic crisis - Firm has a psychological attachment to the employees - Firm vanishes security risks and health incidents to 	Kanban Social cover

	protect employees	
Gender management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Favorizing female responsibility holding as much as male responsibility on tasks and services, - Respecting the gender sense without judging gender choices. 	
Integrity management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Allowing a transversal collaboration between departments and sites - Vanishing different group appartenance and set up a unique identity, regardless of the nationalities, ethnicities, colors or origins - 	Respecting people
Product or process Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Employees must participate in the production and the delivery of valuable content whether materially or mentally. They must avoid any actions that lead to the intrinsic deformation of process against the values of the firm. 	TQM

Source: Authors

The available literature revealed that the effects of cognition, liking, mood, and personality on the performance ratings have all been of great concern for the researchers. Research has examined the link between performance and the personality (Borman & Hallam, 1991; Tziner & Kopelman, 2002); (Bernardin, Cooke, & Villanova, 2000), cognition Woehr, 1992), mood (Sinclair, 1998). Similarly, self-esteem was found to be related to the successful handling of jobs with ambiguous roles (Jex & Elacqua, 1999), acceptance of change (Wanberg & Banas, 2000), motivation and organizational commitment (Hui & Lee, 2000), and resistance to influence (Brockner, 1988). In addition, self-efficacy was found to have a relationship with overall job performance and organizational commitment (Gardner & Pierce, 1998). However, the link between the psychological performance of members and its outcomes does not seem to have been fully explored yet.

Conclusion

If CSR has been underlined by many authors, psychological component has taken less importance in academic research. This micro-element which is related to employee's well-being is the first driver in firm's existence and development. Economic, social and environmental fulfillments can all fall under the misunderstanding of the motivational psychological drivers in employees work satisfaction. In this article, we chose the Lean Management as the example of a philosophy driven by two principle elements: people's respect, and waste elimination, the first one as a good firm engagement in employee's morale. We noticed that even with such a principle, firms are not capable of implementing a psychological system that satisfies employees, since stress, research of perfection, time and

cost constraints are always elements to be managed in a firm, especially the Lean one. These results stimulate as to recognize the importance of establishing a standard, such as environmental standards or CSR guidelines, to help firms manage “employees’ psychology” while seeking better economic results. What was considered yesterday as the image of the firm driven by social and environmental attributes is replaced today by elements such as work stability and reliability that are psychological drivers. The pandemic of COVID 19 has made it prominent for firms to seek a better application of what they perceive as CSR: it’s the wellbeing of employees that are the hard ware of any product or service creation. The Hawthorne experience by Elton Mayo (1880-1949) or the approach of Mary (1868, 1933) were revolutionary issues that dressed the importance of taking care of human beings in the work environment while the main focus was driven toward firm profit, we assist today to the social and environmental responsibility of the firms that is becoming less exact as the psychological drivers are better to study and analysis for the future of corporate resilience especially in the world turbulence effect such as the COVID 19 that needs reliable employees. This reliability is built by many factors such as employee esteem, recognition and trust in making tasks more efficiently and with self-control. Not all firms have arrived to such conclusions or are ready to invest time and costs on taking care of their employees’ minds; however we would like to appoint that today’s CSR academic research focuses only in social and environmental impacts hiding the most critical elements of human satisfaction, the mind, which is the most complex part of CSR. What if CSR was not the question for species protection, what if we were wrong thinking that mental health is an individual issue while it is the solution for CSR objectives? We address the need for strategic management to integrate a new component to the sustainable development requirements which is the employees’ mental health as the most avoided investment field by Firms. What are the costs and the benefits of investing in employees’ mental health?

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